

Tea Quality Prediction by Autoregressive Modeling of Electronic Tongue Signals

Pradip Saha, Santanu Ghorai, Bipan Tudu, Rajib Bandyopadhyay and Nabarun Bhattacharyya

Abstract— In this work, a novel method to model the responses of Electronic Tongue (ET) sensors using autoregressive (AR) and autoregressive moving average (ARMA) techniques is presented. The transient response of each electrode present in the sensor array of an electronic tongue is characterized with tea samples of different qualities. Models coefficients are used as characteristics features of the ET response corresponding to the tea samples. Three different classifiers, namely artificial neural network (ANN), vector valued regularized kernel function approximation (VVRKFA) and one vs. one support vector machine (OVO-SVM), are employed to evaluate the performance of these features to discriminate the quality of black tea. Experimental results on three types of voltammetric measurement data show that the proposed method may be very useful for prediction of tea quality. The present model based classification method is very straightforward and provides better or similar performance compared to some other methods proposed in literature for ET signal classification.

Index Terms— Electronic tongue (ET), feature extraction, autoregressive (AR) model, autoregressive moving average (ARMA) model, OVO-SVM.

I. INTRODUCTION

TEA is one of the most popular beverages consumed across the world. Tea quality evaluation is a vital part of tea processing industry. Conventional means of tea quality estimation make use of different analytical instruments like high performance liquid chromatography [1], gas chromatography [2] and plasma atomic emission spectrometry [3]. All these methods are very expensive, time consuming and requires trained man power. For these reasons, artificial organoleptic systems (AOS) such as electronic nose (EN) and electronic tongue (ET) that can provide fast and repeatable results with higher accuracy is being popular to evaluate tea quality. There are several reviews on applications of electronic

nose [4-7] and ET [8,9] for edible products, agriculture, forestry and pharmaceutical uses, etc. An ET consists of an array of chemical sensors, which generates electronic response based on composition of liquid samples. The response of each sensor of the ET is characterized by a large number of sampled values depending on the measuring principle. Different measurement techniques are used for ET, e.g., voltammetry [10], potentiometry [11], amperometry [12] and impedentiometry [13] and hybrid [14] types ET are reported in literature. The analysis of these ET responses is challenging as the sensors have low selectivity to a specific species and high cross-sensitivity. As a result, ET generates complex and overlapped information about the test sample. Appropriate signal processing and data classification techniques are crucial to facilitate precise interpretation of the complex ET responses.

Several researchers have carried out research work to address this problem by extracting different types of feature sets and by employing diverse classification models. In the literature, there are quite a few works in this field. For example, Scozarri et al. [15] proposed qualitative analysis of water using ET with the help of discrete cosine transform (DCT) based techniques. Moving window-based DCT coefficients are also used by Saha et al. [16] as features to classify by support vector machine (SVM) [17] and vector valued regularized kernel function approximation (VVRKFA) [18] for black tea quality discrimination. Valle et al. [19] and Q. Chen et al. [20] used principal component analysis (PCA) technique for the assessment of water and green tea, respectively, using ET. PCA of ET data fails to provide satisfactory results in many applications. Ivarsson et al. [21] showed that PCA analysis of pulse voltametry data provides poor classification accuracy. They achieved improved discrimination of nine different types of tea by combining large amplitude pulse voltametry (LAPV) and staircase voltametry data by multivariate data analysis (MVDA) and principal component analysis (PCA). Palit et al. [22] classified Indian black tea by using discrete wavelet transform (DWT) features of voltametric ET data by artificial neural network (ANN) [23].

Previous literature has shown that researchers have utilized mainly DCT, DWT and PCA features for ET based signal processing and feature extraction in tandem with classification algorithms like linear discrimination analysis (LDA), ANN, SVM, VVRKFA. These approaches were used to reduce the dimensionality of the ET data based on signal transformation techniques. However, there has been no previous investigation to model the responses of ET sensors. In this work, we have

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made an attempt to model the time series response of all the sensors of an ET corresponding to different qualities of tea samples by Autoregressive (AR) and autoregressive moving average (ARMA) modeling techniques [24-25]. The ability of AR and ARMA model coefficients as the attribute to distinguish the responses of ET for four different qualities of Indian black tea sample is studied. The objectives of the research work are as follows:

- I. To validate the experimental results on three different types of voltammetric ET signals, namely large amplitude pulse voltammetry (LAPV), small amplitude pulse voltammetry (SAPV) and staircase voltammetry;
- II. To study the effect of variation of AR and ARMA model orders on classification performance;
- III. To establish the efficacy of the model coefficients as features for addressing the ET signal discrimination by more than one classifier, namely artificial neural network (ANN), vector valued regularized kernel function approximation (VVRKFA) and multiclass support vector machine (SVM) classifier.

Our preceding research work revealed that sliding window based DWT features [26] can classify three types of pulse voltammetry data very effectively. But this technique has the drawback that it is complicated and takes large time to test an unknown ET signal, as the final decision is made based on evaluation on a number of windowed signals. Compared to this context, the present model based classification method is very straightforward and fast. Further, it does not require combining several types of data for accurate prediction as pointed out by Ivarsson et al. [21]. Experimental results show that the proposed model based analysis of ET signal may be effective for black tea quality estimation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the details of the proposed feature extraction method and prediction technique. The experimental setup, results and corresponding analysis are shown in section III. Finally, in section IV conclusions from the work are mentioned.

II. PROPOSED FEATURE EXTRACTION METHOD FOR TEA QUALITY ESTIMATION

A measurement in a multi-electrode system is represented by a large number of measured values. For example, Fig. 1 shows the transient response as obtained from an ET using staircase voltammetry. This shows the output current response collected from each of five electrodes in a sequential manner corresponding to each applied voltage level. This one-dimensional representation of ET signal corresponds to large number of sampled output for each test sample. Interpretation of these data requires proper signal processing and analysis techniques. Fig. 2 shows the PCA plot of the measurement data obtained by staircase voltammetry method. The plot makes clear that simple PCA analysis is not competent to discriminate the ET data accurately. Usually, the categorization of the sample requires efficient signal processing techniques along with some machine learning algorithms. In order to analyze these data, we consider the ET signal as a multi-dimensional signal produced by five electrodes simultaneously due to the application of pulse

voltage input as shown in fig. 3. If the ET signal is considered as one-dimensional signal then the signals from different sensors may lose the information of occurrences of dissimilar frequency components. With the intention of ET signal interpretation we have modeled the dynamics of ET response by using AR and ARMA modeling techniques. Here, AR and ARMA models are used to represent the dynamic response of each electrode. AR coefficients are computed using Burg's algorithm whereas the coefficients of ARMA process are estimated by minimizing a quadratic prediction error criterion.

A. Autoregressive Model

The advantage of AR modeling is its simplicity due to the linear form of the system and is suitable for real-time classification. AR model [24-25] of order j , $AR(j)$, is used to represent a signal sequence or, in other words, the response of i th electrode $y^i(n)$ for a particular tea sample can be expressed by

$$y^i(n) = c_1^i y(n-1) + c_2^i y(n-2) + \dots + c_j^i y(n-j) + \varepsilon(n) + c \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Transient response of ET for staircase.

Fig. 2. PCA plot of the measurement data obtained by staircase voltammetry method.

Fig. 3. Typical response of ET using staircase method.

where c_k^i ($k = 1, 2, \dots, j$) are the autoregressive parameters or model coefficients $\varepsilon(n)$ is a zero mean white noise series and

c is a constant. The model order j indicates that previous j samples are used to predict the present output value. The estimated AR model having the same order, j can be represented by,

$$\hat{y}^i(n) = \hat{c}_1^i y(n-1) + \hat{c}_2^i y(n-2) + \dots + \hat{c}_j^i y(n-j) + \hat{\varepsilon}(n), \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{c}_k^i (k=1,2,\dots,j)$ represent the estimated autoregressive model coefficients and $\hat{\varepsilon}(n)$ are the estimated innovations. An estimated $AR(j)$ model can be realized as the j -point prediction filter where the present value of the filter output, $\hat{y}^i(n)$, is determined by the past $j-1$ output values of the autoregressive process and can be expressed as,

$$\hat{y}^i(n) = \sum_{k=1}^j \hat{c}_k^i y(n-k). \quad (3)$$

Estimation of autoregressive parameters of the AR model is accomplished by using different methods namely: Yule-Walker method (YW), least-square method (LS), and Burg's method [24-25], [27]. Each of the methods has its own advantages and disadvantages. In this work, we have used Burg's method to estimate the AR model parameters as this method is preferred over referable due to the instability of the LS method and poor estimation by YW method [28].

Fig. 4. Original and predicted signal by 2nd order AR model for (a) LAPV (b) SAPV and (c) Staircase type measurements of ET signal.

Burg's method uses LS criteria to find out the reflection coefficients of the equivalent lattice structure predictor filter and then Levinson-Durbin algorithm [24-25] is used to

estimate AR model parameters. Finally, the feature vector of a sample for j th order AR model is formed by taking the model parameters of $k (k=1,2,\dots,5)$ electrodes of ET system as follows:

$$f = [\hat{c}_1^1, \hat{c}_2^1, \dots, \hat{c}_j^1, \hat{c}_1^2, \hat{c}_2^2, \dots, \hat{c}_j^2, \dots, \hat{c}_1^k, \hat{c}_2^k, \dots, \hat{c}_j^k]. \quad (4)$$

Thus, as an example, the length of a feature for a 5 electrodes ET system with 2nd order AR model will be 10. Fig. 4 shows the performance of 2nd order AR model to predict output signal of the gold sensor for class-5 tea sample for three different types of voltammetric measurements using ET. The peaks in this figure are prediction errors of the models arise mainly due to the sudden hop of the signal. The average root mean square error (RMSE) to predict the response of gold sensor by 2nd order AR model for LAPV, SAPV and STAIRCASE data are observed as 0.2270, 0.1841 and 0.2443, respectively.

B. Autoregressive Moving Average Model

ARMA model [24-25] is nothing but the combination of AR model that includes the lagged terms on the time series itself and MA model that includes the lagged terms on the noise or residuals. The order of the ARMA model is specified by $ARMA(a,m)$, where a is the AR order and m is the MA order. The advantage of ARMA modeling is its higher flexibility in the fitting of actual time series as it incorporates both AR terms and MA terms. ARMA model of order (a,m) , $ARMA(a,m)$, is used to represent a signal sequence or in other words the response of i th electrode $y_i(t)$ for a particular tea sample can be expressed by

$$y^i(n) = \alpha_1^i y(n-1) + \alpha_2^i y(n-2) + \dots + \alpha_a^i y(n-a) + \varepsilon(n) + \beta_1^i \varepsilon(n-1) + \beta_2^i \varepsilon(n-2) + \dots + \beta_m^i \varepsilon(n-m), \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_k^i (k=1,2,\dots,a)$ are the autoregressive parameters and $\beta_k^i (k=1,2,\dots,m)$ are the moving average parameters or in other words these are the model coefficients and $\varepsilon(n)$ is a zero mean white noise series. The estimated ARMA model having same order as (a,m) , can be represented by

$$\hat{y}^i(n) = \hat{\alpha}_1^i y(n-1) + \hat{\alpha}_2^i y(n-2) + \dots + \hat{\alpha}_a^i y(n-a) + \hat{\varepsilon}(n) + \hat{\beta}_1^i \varepsilon(n-1) + \hat{\beta}_2^i \varepsilon(n-2) + \dots + \hat{\beta}_m^i \varepsilon(n-m), \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_k^i (k=1,2,\dots,a)$ and $\hat{\beta}_k^i (k=1,2,\dots,m)$ represents the estimated ARMA model coefficients and $\hat{\varepsilon}(n)$ are the estimated innovations. An estimated $ARMA(a,m)$ model can be expressed as,

$$\hat{y}^i(n) = \sum_{k=1}^a \hat{\alpha}_k^i y(n-k) + \sum_{k=1}^m \hat{\beta}_k^i y(n-k). \quad (7)$$

Estimation of parameters of the ARMA model is obtained by using canonical variate analysis (CVA) method [29]. The feature vector of a sample for $ARMA(a,m)$ model is formed by considering the model parameters of $k (k=1,2,\dots,5)$ electrodes of ET system as follows:

$$f = [\hat{\alpha}_1^1, \hat{\alpha}_2^1, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_a^1, \hat{\beta}_1^1, \hat{\beta}_2^1, \dots, \hat{\beta}_m^1, \hat{\alpha}_1^2, \hat{\alpha}_2^2, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_a^2, \hat{\beta}_1^2, \hat{\beta}_2^2, \dots, \hat{\beta}_m^2, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_1^k, \hat{\alpha}_2^k, \dots, \hat{\alpha}_a^k, \hat{\beta}_1^k, \hat{\beta}_2^k, \dots, \hat{\beta}_m^k] \quad (8)$$

Thus, the length of a feature vector for a 5 electrodes ET system with $ARMA(2,2)$ model will be 20. The average RMSE to predict the response of gold sensor by using $ARMA(2,2)$ model for LAPV, SAPV and STAIRCASE data sets are obtained as 0.2235, 0.1593 and 0.1765, respectively.

C. Classifiers

In order to ensure that the features are efficiently performing well the task of tea quality prediction, they are tested with three different classifiers. Brief descriptions of these classifiers are given below:

1. ANN: ANN is a well known efficient tool for classification and function approximation [23]. Its detailed description is omitted here. A three layer back propagation multilayer perceptron (BP-MLP) network model is considered in this work.

2. VVRKFA: This is a recently developed multiclass data classification approach by means of vector-valued regression of the patterns from the feature space to the label space using kernel trick [18]. It eliminates the drawback of decomposition techniques of a multiclass data classification problem. Detail description and application of VVRKFA can be found in [18].

3. SVM: SVM is a widely used supervised binary classifier based on the structural risk minimization (SRM) principle [17]. In a binary classification problem, SVM finds an optimal separating hyperplane that maximizes the separation between the two classes by solving a quadratic optimization problem. There are several techniques to extend binary classifier into multiclass classifier [30]. Among these the common decomposition techniques are one-vs.-one (OVO), one-vs.-rest (OVR), and directed acyclic graph (DAG) etc. Hsu and Lin [30] showed that the performance of the OVO SVM classifier is better than the other methods. For a N class problem, OVO method trains ${}^N C_2$ numbers of binary classifier models. The class label of an unknown sample is decided by the maximum vote in favor to a particular class. In this application we have used OVO SVM classifier.

III. EXPERIMENTATION

A. Electronic Tongue System

We have used the pulse voltammetric type ET system developed in our LAB. Details of this system are described in our previous research work [22]. It consists of five different noble metal type working electrodes namely, gold, iridium, rhodium, palladium, and platinum, a platinum counter electrode (PH Ionics, India) and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (saturated KCl, Gamry Instruments Inc., USA). A picture of the ET system is shown in fig. 5. There are five different modules namely, sensor array, software based signal generation unit along with a switching circuit, data acquisition card, level shifter with amplifier and a virtual instrumentation system (VIS) along with signal processing and data analysis

unit within it. Different types of pulses are generated by using LabVIEW based VIS and a low-cost multifunctional data acquisition card USB 6008 of National Instruments having frequency 100 Hz is used to perform data acquisition. Pulse waveforms with different amplitudes selected by the users in small steps with the range of 0 to 500 mV is generated by the VIS and then the waveform is amplified by two times using an amplifier and shifted negatively by 200 mV using a level shifter to obtain a signal varying from -0.2 V to +0.8 V. This signal is applied to the test samples through one of five working electrodes one at a time where the sequence is maintained by a switching circuit. In case of staircase waveform, 760 data points are recorded for each of five electrodes and as a result the total response consists of $5 \times 760 = 3800$ measurement points for a single run. Thus, the actual dimension of each run for a particular sample is 1×3800 but in this work it is considered as multi-signal having 5×760 data points. Similarly, in case of SAPV and LAPV waveforms, instead of 1×3470 dimensions, we have considered 5×694 data points.

Fig. 5. A picture of the compact electronic tongue system used for experiment.

B. Sample collection and preparation

Four different grades of tea samples were collected from Kanan Devan Hill Plantation, situated in Southern India. The quality of the tea was estimated by a sensory panel of five tea tasters. The average of their decisions was taken as the quality of the tea score. Table I describes a sample tea tasters' score against 'strength' of the liquor without milk and is based on the combined perception of taste, astringency and briskness of the tea samples varying in the range 5 to 8. The response of ET is collected from the liquor of tea sample, prepared by boiling 200ml of de-ionized water poured over 750 mg of dry tea sample and brewed for 5 minutes. To separate the tea leaves, the solution is passed through a filter paper and then the solution is kept at room temperature for 20 minutes. After this the samples are ready for measurements with the sensor array in ET where the readings are recorded. We have recorded 694 data points from each of the five electrodes in LAPV and SAPV method and 760 data points in staircase method. The electrodes are cleaned with distilled water after each run. In this work, the number of samples used for LAPV, SAPV and staircase methods are, respectively, 95, 98 and 90.

TABLE I
SAMPLE TEA TASTER'S SCORE

Sample code	Scores (1-10)		
	Leaf quality	Aroma	Strength
11000	5	4	5
11001	5	4	6
11002	6	4	5
11004	8	6	7
11005	7	5	6
11006	7	5	6
11007	7	6	7
11008	7	6	7
11009	8	5	7
11011	8	6	8

C. Experimental Procedure

We have studied the performance of the proposed feature extraction method on three types of voltametric data sets. For each data set we have observed the effect of model order on the classification accuracy of ANN, VVRKFA and OVO-SVM classifiers. In order to implement ANN classifier, a network structure with three layers, input layer, one hidden layer and an output layer is considered. The optimal number of neurons in the hidden layer is selected as 10 by varying it from 5 to 30. The learning rate factor and momentum factor are all set to 0.1; the initial weights are assigned randomly; activation functions for hidden layer and output layer are set as the 'sigmoid' and 'linear' functions, respectively. Gaussian kernel is used to evaluate performance of VVRKFA and OVO-SVM. The optimal values of the regularized parameter C for VVRKFA and SVM are selected from the sets $\{10^i \mid i = -6, -5, \dots, -2\}$ and $\{2^i \mid i = -7, -6, \dots, 15\}$, respectively. The Gaussian kernel parameter μ for both the methods is selected from the set $\{2^i \mid i = -10, -9, \dots, 9, 10\}$. The values of the optimal parameters are selected by comparing the performance of the classifier on a tuning set formed by 20% of training data and the rest of training data are used to train the classifier [31]. All the training data are normalized in the range [0 1]. Leave-one-out cross validation (LOO-CV) technique [31] is used to evaluate the performance of the classifiers on total data set using selected optimal parameters. Results are observed by varying the model orders from 2 to 10. For ARMA model, we have considered same orders of AR and MA process to get a consistent amount of features.

D. Experimental Results

1) Results on LAPV data

Table II shows the average LOO-CV accuracies and standard deviations of ANN, VVRKFA and SVM classifiers using AR and ARMA model parameters of orders from 2 to 10 of LAPV data set. The highest accuracy of each classification method is in bold case. From table II, it is observed that all the three classifiers can provide very high classification accuracy using AR model coefficients. Different classifiers provide the highest accuracies with different model orders. For example, ANN provides 95.79% with 4th order AR model whereas VVRKFA and SVM provide 98.95% with 6th and 7th orders

AR model, respectively. However, classification accuracies using ARMA model parameters are not as good as AR model parameters. The classification accuracy decreases for all the methods as the model order increases from 2. It is also observed that performances of both VVRKFA and SVM are better than that of ANN for both AR and ARMA models.

2) Results on SAPV data

Performance on SAPV data set is shown in table III. It shows that the performances of all the three classifiers on SAPV data are reduced compared to the performances on LAPV data. Among the three classifiers, VVRKFA provides the highest classification accuracy of 88.78% with a high standard deviation of 31.57% on both 7th and 8th order AR model features. Performance on ARMA model coefficients is further reduced with the highest classification accuracy of 79.59% with a standard deviation of 40.30% obtained by VVRKFA on 2nd order model. Again, the classification accuracy decreases gradually for all the three methods using ARMA model parameters as the model order increases from 2.

TABLE II
LOO-CV PERFORMANCE ON LAPV DATA SET

Model type	Model order	Avg. % LOO-CV testing accuracy (\pm std.)		
		ANN	VVRKFA	OVO-SVM
AR	2	94.74(22.32)	87.37(33.22)	96.84(17.49)
	3	91.58(27.77)	94.74(22.33)	96.84(17.49)
	4	95.79(20.08)	96.84(17.49)	97.89(14.36)
	5	90.53(29.28)	95.79(20.08)	97.89(14.36)
	6	88.42(31.99)	97.89(14.36)	98.95(10.21)
	7	92.63(26.12)	98.95(10.21)	97.89(14.36)
	8	88.42(31.99)	96.84(17.49)	96.84(17.49)
	9	84.21(36.46)	96.84(17.49)	92.63(26.13)
	10	91.58(27.77)	90.53(29.29)	90.53(29.29)
	ARMA	(2,2)	86.32(34.66)	95.79(20.08)
(3,3)		86.32(34.66)	86.32(34.37)	90.53(29.29)
(4,4)		70.53(45.59)	77.89(41.50)	72.63(44.58)
(5,5)		43.16(49.52)	62.11(48.51)	61.05(48.76)
(6,6)		34.74(47.61)	51.58(49.98)	43.16(49.53)
(7,7)		37.89(48.51)	60.00(48.99)	46.32(49.86)
(8,8)		30.53(46.05)	57.89(49.37)	50.53(50.00)
(9,9)		43.16(49.52)	54.74(49.78)	52.63(49.93)
(10,10)		27.37(44.58)	35.79(47.94)	37.89(48.51)

3) Results on staircase data

Performances of AR and ARMA model coefficients for staircase data set are shown in table IV. From table IV it is observed that both VVRKFA and SVM provide the highest accuracy of 98.89% and standard deviation of 10.48% with a 5th and 3rd, 8th order models, respectively. Compared to this ANN classifier provides a maximum accuracy of 88.89% and standard deviation of 31.42% with 4th order AR model. Performance of ARMA model parameters is not as good as AR model parameters. A maximum classification accuracy of 63.33% by ANN and 85.56% by both VVRKFA and SVM are obtained by using 2nd order ARMA model parameters.

4) Analysis of results

The key observations from the experimental results of tables II, III and IV may be summarized as below:

- i) Performances of ARMA models are moderately poor compared to the performances of AR models.
- ii) Kernel classifiers, such as VVRKFA and SVM, perform

better than ANN classifier using the AR model coefficients for all the three types of data sets. This fact is clear from the fig. 6. It shows the variation of classification accuracies of the three classifiers using AR model parameters with the increase of model order.

- iii) It is observed from the fig. 6 that as the model order of AR process increases, the classification accuracy also increases and attains a maximum value for a certain order and then decreases gradually. This indicates choice of model order for ET signal classification is important for accurate classification.
- iv) From the results on three types of data, it is observed that classification accuracies using AR model coefficients on SAPV data are not as good as LAPV or staircase data.

TABLE III
LOO-CV PERFORMANCE ON SAPV DATA SET

Model type	Model order	Avg. % LOO CV testing accuracy (\pm std.)		
		ANN	VVRKFA	OVO-SVM
AR	2	53.06(49.90)	69.39(46.09)	63.16(48.24)
	3	56.12(49.26)	78.57(41.03)	72.11(44.55)
	4	60.20(48.94)	80.61(39.53)	85.79(34.54)
	5	56.12(49.62)	86.73(33.92)	80.00(40.00)
	6	54.08(49.83)	87.76(32.78)	78.95(40.12)
	7	56.12(49.62)	88.78(31.57)	73.16(44.02)
	8	60.20(48.94)	88.78(31.57)	68.95(45.99)
	9	65.31(47.59)	81.63(38.72)	64.74(47.50)
	10	59.18(49.14)	81.63(38.72)	63.68(47.82)
	ARMA	(2,2)	54.08(49.83)	79.59(40.30)
(3,3)		37.76(48.74)	42.86(49.49)	46.32(49.86)
(4,4)		39.80(48.94)	38.78(48.72)	37.89(47.97)
(5,5)		44.90(49.73)	30.61(46.09)	43.86(49.33)
(6,6)		27.55(44.67)	26.53(44.15)	35.79(47.39)
(7,7)		38.78(48.72)	47.96(49.96)	31.05(45.99)
(8,8)		25.51(43.59)	36.73(48.21)	30.00(45.54)
(9,9)		36.73(48.20)	34.69(47.60)	27.36(44.58)
(10,10)		28.57(45.17)	40.82(49.18)	42.11(49.37)

TABLE IV
LOO-CV PERFORMANCE ON STAIRCASE DATA SET

Model type	Model order	Avg. % LOO-CV testing accuracy (\pm std.)		
		ANN	VVRKFA	OVO-SVM
AR	2	65.56(47.51)	88.89(31.43)	91.11(28.46)
	3	87.78(32.75)	97.78(14.74)	98.89(10.48)
	4	88.89(31.42)	95.56(20.61)	97.78(14.74)
	5	85.56(35.15)	98.89(10.48)	97.78(14.74)
	6	83.33(37.26)	97.78(14.74)	94.44(22.91)
	7	78.89(40.80)	95.56(20.61)	93.33(24.94)
	8	83.33(37.26)	95.56(20.61)	98.89(10.48)
	9	78.89(40.80)	94.44(22.91)	92.22(26.78)
	10	75.56(42.97)	92.22(26.78)	88.89(31.43)
	ARMA	(2,2)	63.33(48.18)	85.56(35.15)
(3,3)		56.67(49.55)	66.67(47.14)	72.22(44.79)
(4,4)		50.00(50.00)	63.33(48.19)	63.33(48.19)
(5,5)		46.67(49.88)	53.33(49.89)	48.89(49.99)
(6,6)		33.33(47.14)	46.67(49.89)	33.33(47.14)
(7,7)		40.00(48.98)	54.44(49.80)	43.33(49.55)
(8,8)		28.89(45.32)	38.89(48.75)	28.89(45.32)
(9,9)		31.11(46.29)	41.11(49.20)	32.22(46.73)
(10,10)		22.22(41.57)	24.44(42.98)	27.78(44.49)

The difference in performance of the proposed ET signal classification by AR model coefficients on LAPV and SAPV data sets may be explained with the help of box plots as shown in Fig. 7. The figure shows the normalized feature values of

AR model coefficients of four grades of tea samples, specified as 1, 2, 3 and 4, for all the ten features from F_1 to F_{10} of 2nd order model. From the figs. 7(a) and 7(b), it is observed that the features obtained from AR model coefficients for LAPV data set are less overlapped compared to that of SAPV data set. In other words, this demonstrates that AR model coefficients for SAPV data are less discriminative than that of LAPV data. As a result, SAPV data are not highly classifiable and this fact is reflected in the classification performance shown in table III. The nature of the feature values obtained from staircase data set is almost similar to the features obtained from LAPV data set. Consequently, good classification accuracy is achieved on LAPV and staircase data sets compared to SAPV data.

Fig.6 LOO-CV performance of extracted features by ANN, VVRKFA and SVM for AR models with the variation of model order for (a) LAPV (b) SAPV and (c) Staircase type measurements of ET signal.

5) Comparison with other methods

The performance of the proposed method is compared to that of four other feature extraction methods, namely sliding window based Haar wavelet features [26], sliding window based DCT features [16], 6th level discrete wavelet features with Haar wavelet [22] and first five principal component [20] of ET signals. In order to compare the quality of the features, the experiment is performed with different feature sets extracted from the ET signal under identical conditions by SVM classifier. We have considered the highest average LOO-CV classification accuracy obtained by the methods for comparison. It is observed from the results shown in table V

that the performance AR model parameters offered the highest classification accuracy of 98.95% on LAPV and 98.89% on staircase data sets. Methods of [26] and [22] also provide the same accuracy of 98.95% on LAPV data set. The method of [26] provides the best accuracy among all the methods on SAPV data. This shows that proposed ET signal classification by AR model coefficients is comparable or even better than other methods for LAPV and staircase data. However, performance of ARMA model coefficients is not as good as AR coefficients or other methods.

Fig. 7 Box plots of the features of four classes obtained from the 2nd order AR model coefficients for (a) LAPV and (b) SAPV data sets.

TABLE V
COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE WITH OTHER METHODS

Methods and features	% LOO CV accuracy (\pm std.) on		
	LAPV	SAPV	STAIRCASE
Sliding window (window size=64) based Haar wavelet features [26]	98.95 (10.21)	97.96 (14.14)	92.22 (26.78)
Sliding window (window size=128) based DCT features [16]	97.89 (14.64)	86.28 (19.89)	86.89 (10.92)
6 th level discrete Haar wavelet coefficients [22]	98.95 (10.21)	96.94 (17.23)	97.78 (14.74)
PCA features (first 5 PC's) [20]	93.47 (10.24)	71.84 (18.92)	87.11 (15.29)
Proposed AR model coefficients	98.95 (10.21)	88.78 (31.57)	98.89 (10.48)
Proposed ARMA model coefficients	97.89 (14.36)	79.59 (40.30)	85.56 (35.15)

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have proposed a model based classification of electronic tongue signal using AR and ARMA models. The model coefficients are used as characteristic features of the four different qualities of tea samples. The method presented in this work using AR coefficients as features is easy to

develop from the response of ET signal. The testing of a new sample in this method is fast compared to the sliding window based technique [16], [26]. Thus, classification of tea samples using AR model coefficients is observed effective for LAPV and staircase type of measurements. As these linear model coefficients are not effective for SAPV type of measurement, future research work may include probabilistic modeling, kernel-based nonlinear modeling, etc., to improve the performance of classification on all types of ET signal measurements.

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